

Evaluation of USG Findings and FNAC Findings in the Diagnosis of Thyroid Lesions: A Correlative Study

Thakur Haridayal Singh

Associate Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Pratima Institute of Medical Sciences, Nagunoor, Karimnagar, Telangana

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Thakur Haridayal Singh

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Thyroid gland is unique endocrine gland and is vulnerable to the lesions. USG is primary choice of imaging technique to evaluate thyroid morphology due to its high sensitivity for nodular detection. FNAC is a sensitive investigative tool with 97% of diagnostic accuracy. This study was aimed to evaluate the USG and FNAC in the diagnosis of cases with thyroid lesions.

Methods: A total 100 cases with thyroid disorders between age group 2nd to 7th decades were recruited. All the cases were subjected to detailed clinical examination and then subjected to ultrasonographic evaluation. Radiologically confirmed cases with thyroid lesions were subjected to FNAC.

Results: Microcalcification was seen in 35.2% cases, Macrocalcification in 14.7% and no calcification in 26.4% cases. In USG diagnosis, 53.7% nodules were >1cm in size, Isoechogenic nodules was seen in 32.3%, Hyper echogenic in 29.4%, Hypoechoic in 17.6% and anechoic nodules in 23.5% cases. USG findings was correlated with FNAC findings in 3% of medullary carcinoma cases, 5% of papillary carcinoma, 41% of thyroiditis cases, 14% of MNG cases, 25% of colloid goiter cases and 12% of adenomatous nodule.

Conclusion: USG is a non-invasive procedure when compared to FNAC. In this study, USG showed best outcome in related to diagnose the features of thyroid nodules such as size, echogenesity, peripeheral halo, calcification and vascularity. USG is best image based diagnostic tool in the diagnosis of malignant and benign type of thyroid lesions, when it combines with US guided FNAC it can give still accurate results.

Keywords: Ultrasonography (USG), Fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC), Thyroid lesions, Malignant, Sensitivity, Specificity.

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Introduction

Lesions to the thyroid gland are a common surgical and endocrine problem occurs in general medical practice with an incidence of 4-8% [1, 2]. In majority cases it is usually occurs after 65 years of age with female predominance [3]. Among the available diagnostic modalities Ultrasonography (USG) and Fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) are commonly used tools for thyroid lesions [4].

In cases with thyroid lesions, colour Doppler and gray scale USG were used to assess its sonographic features such as size of nodule, composition, echogenesity, peripeheral halo, calcification and vascularity. USG has higher resolution, helps in the detection of non-palpable lesion and aspiration of distrustful nodules [5].

FNAC is an accurate laboratory diagnostic tool which provides accurate details of lesions and become reason for reducing thyroidectomy approximately 50% [6,7]. With reference of above literature this prospective study was aimed to

evaluate the USG and FNAC in the diagnosis of cases with thyroid lesions.

Materials and Methods

The present prospective study was conducted in Department of Radiodiagnosis, Pratima Institute of Medical Sciences, Karimnagar from April 2023 to March 2024.

A total 100 cases with thyroid disorders between age group 2nd to 7th decades were included. Cases who are willing to participate, age group between 11-70 years and cases with thyroid lesions were included and cases with other than thyroid lesions, not willing to participate in the study were excluded from the study.

Verbal informed consent was obtained from all the cases and study protocol was approved by the institutional ethics committee. All the cases were subjected to detailed clinical examination and then subjected to ultrasonographic evaluation.

Radiologically confirmed cases with thyroid lesions were subjected to FNAC. A 23-27 G needle linked to 10 cc syringe was used for the aspiration and then biopsy specimen sent to pathological investigation. Identification of follicular lesions is difficult with USG and FNAC. Follicular lesions are termed as adenomatous nodules in USG and follicular neoplasm in FNAC.

For statistical analysis, Data was extracted and percentages was calculated by using Microsoft excel sheet. Fisher's exact test was used to estimate sensitivity, Specificity, Diagnostic accuracy rate,

positive predictive value and negative predictive value.

Results:

Total 100 cases clinically diagnosed and conformed to various thyroid lesions between age group 11-70 years were considered.

Among the participants majority were between age group 3rd to 6th decades (87%) (Table 1). Majority cases with thyroid lesions were females (88%) than males (12%).

Table 1: Age wise distribution of cases

Age (In years)	Cases	
	Number	Percentage
11-20	08	8%
21-30	12	12%
31-40	24	24%
41-50	32	32%
51-60	19	19%
61-70	05	5%

Table 2: Distribution of cases based on Echo texture and vascularity of thyroid parenchyma

Echo texture	Cases	
	Number	Percentage
Homogenous	39	39%
Heterogenous	61	61%
Vascularity		
Normal	44	44%
Increased	56	56%

In the present study 39% cases had homogenous echotexture of thyroid parenchyma, whereas 61% cases had heterogenous echotexture of thyroid parenchyma (Table 2). In 56% cases found increased vascular supply to thyroid gland whereas in 44% cases vascular supply was normal (Table 2). Nodules were seen in 88% cases.

Table 3: Thyroid lesion distribution based on FNAC findings

Details of Thyroid nodules	Malignant (n=5)		Benign (n=43)	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
A. Size of the nodule				
<5mm	-	-	02	4.65%
5mm-1cm	01	20%	12	27.9%
>1cm	04	80%	29	67.4%
B. Echogenicity of thyroid lesions				
Hypoechogenic	03	60%	06	13.9%
Isoechogenic	01	20%	16	37.2%
Hyperechogenic	01	20%	09	20.9%
Anechoic	00	-	12	27.9%
C. Calcification of lesions				
Macrocalcification	01	20%	05	11.62%
Microcalcification	02	40%	10	23.2%
Rimcalcification	01	20%	12	27.9%
No calcification	01	20%	16	37.2%

In FNAC, multiple nodules were seen in 71% cases and single nodule was seen in 29% cases. Solid type of nodules was seen in 33.3% cases and cystic type of nodule was seen in 66.6% cases. In benign type, <5mm size lesions were seen in 4.65%, 5mm-1cm lesion were seen in 27.9% and >1cm lesion were seen in 67.4% (Table 3). Hypervascularity was seen in both benign and malignant lesions.

Table 4: Thyroid lesion distribution based on USG findings

Distribution of thyroid lesions by USG	Thyroid nodules	
	Number	Percentage
A. Size of the nodule		
<5mm	15	27.7%
5mm-1cm	10	18.5%
>1cm	29	53.7%
B. Echogenicity of thyroid lesions		
Hypoechogenic	06	17.6%
Isoechogenic	11	32.3%
Hyperechogenic	10	29.4%
Anechoic	08	23.5%
C. Calcification of lesions		
Macrocalcification	05	14.7%
Microcalcification	12	35.2%
Rimcalcification	08	23.5%
No calcification	09	26.4%

In USG diagnosis, 53.7% nodules were >1cm in size. Isoechogenic nodules was seen in 32.3%, Hyperechogenic nodules was seen in 29.4%, Hypoechogenic nodules was seen in 17.6% and anechoic nodules was seen in 23.5% cases (Table 4).

Table 5: Comparison and correlation between USG findings with FNAC findings

Condition	USG/FNAC		Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV
	No.	%				
Medullary carcinoma	03	3%	100	100	100	0
Papillary carcinoma	05	5%	85.3	78.6	65.3	34.7
Thyroiditis	41	41%	88.9	91.4	94.6	5.4
MNG	14	14%	99	98.1	100	0
Colloid goiter	25	25%	86.6	74.8	95.3	4.7
Adenomatous nodule	12	12%	88.3	77	69.5	30.5

USG findings was correlated with FNAC findings in 3% of medullary carcinoma cases, 5% of papillary carcinoma, 41% of thyroiditis cases, 14% of MNG cases, 25% of colloid goiter cases and 12% of adenomatous nodule cases. Sensitivity, specificity and PPV were 100% in diagnosis of medullary carcinoma. In the diagnosis of thyroiditis, sensitivity was 88.9%, specificity was 91.4%, PPV was 94.6% and NPV was 5.4%. Whereas for the papillary carcinoma, sensitivity was 85.3%, specificity was 78.6%, PPV was 65.3% and NPV was 34.7% (Table 5).

Discussion

Ultrasonography, a common imaging modality after clinical examination. FNAC is a well-developed diagnostic tool for the surgical and non-surgical thyroid lesions [8]. The present study was aimed to correlate the findings of ultrasonography and FNAC in thyroid lesion cases. A total 100 cases clinically diagnosed and conformed thyroid lesions were considered. Among the participants majority were between age group 3rd to 6th decades (87%) (Table 1). Majority cases with thyroid lesions were females (88%) than males (12%). In the present study 39% cases had homogenous echotexture of thyroid parenchyma, whereas 61% cases had homogenous echotexture of thyroid

parenchyma. In 56% cases found increased vascular supply to thyroid gland whereas in 44% cases vascular supply was normal (Table 2).

Study by CH Vittal Prasad et al., found hypoechoic nodules in 72% cases [8]. Study by Won-Jin Moon, et al., and Enrido papini et al., found hypoechoic nodules in 87% cases (9, 10), whereas study by M.C. Frateset, et al., found hypoechoic nodules in 26.5%-87.1% cases [11]. In this study, USG found hypoechoic nodules in 17.6% cases and hyperechoic nodules were found in 29.4% cases Isoechogenic nodules were found in 32.3% cases and anechoic nodules were found in 23.5% cases (Table 4).

In this study microcalcification was seen in 35.2% cases, Macrocalcification was seen in 14.7% cases and no calcification was seen in 26.4% cases. Study by CH Vittal Prasad et al., found microcalcification in 68% cases, Won-Jin Moon, et al., in 44% and Enrido papini et al., in 29% and M.C. Frateset, et al., in 26.1%-59.1% [8-11]. Study by Gururaj sharma et al., found macrocalcification in 35.7% malignant nodules and 22.5% in benign nodules [13]. Studies suggested that microcalcification was frequent in malignant nodules than benign nodules [9, 14, 15].

In present study, USG findings were correlated with FNAC findings in 3% of medullary carcinoma cases, 5% of papillary carcinoma, 41% of thyroiditis cases, 14% of MNG cases, 25% of colloid goiter cases and 12% of adenomatous nodule cases. USG has sensitivity, specificity and PPV 100% for medullary carcinoma diagnosis. In the diagnosis of thyroiditis, USG has sensitivity of 88.9%, specificity of 91.4%, PPV of 94.6% and NPV of 5.4%. Whereas for the papillary carcinoma, sensitivity was 85.3%, specificity was 78.6%, PPV was 65.3% and NPV was 34.7%. For adenomatous nodule sensitivity was 88.3%, specificity was 77%, PPV was 69.5% and NPV was 30.5% (Table 5). Study by Lokhande et al., stated that USG has sensitivity 71.43%, specificity 90.62% and accuracy 87.18% [16]. Vikas et al., stated sensitivity of thyroid ultrasound for diagnosing a malignant nodule is 83.3% [17].

Conclusion

USG is a primary choice of imaging method to evaluate the cases with thyroid lesions such as multinodular goiter, thyroiditis, and medullary carcinoma. USG is a non-invasive procedure when compared to FNAC. In this study, USG showed best outcome in related to diagnose the features of thyroid nodules such as size, echogenesity, peripeheral halo, calcification and vascularity. USG findings were correlated with FNAC findings in 3% of medullary carcinoma cases, 5% of papillary carcinoma, 41% of thyroiditis cases, 14% of MNG cases, 25% of colloid goiter cases and 12% of adenomatous nodule cases. USG is best image based diagnostic tool in the diagnosis of malignant and benign type of thyroid lesions, when it combines with US guided FNAC it can give still accurate results. Further studies are required to assess the efficacy of same with USG guided FNAC with more samples.

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